

Study of Need of Walking and Jogging to Maintain Physical and Mental Health

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Abstract:

Walking or running is extremely useful for physical and mental health. It strengthens the nerve and muscle cells in the human body. Reduces unwanted body fat thus helps in weight loss. The mind and body remain energetic. It helps to stay free from stress. Improves digestion, enhances the body's immune system, and helps to increase memory, Toxins are also expelled from the body so that the body is cleansed. It also helps to improve breathing process, etc. There are many benefits of walking and running therefore, each person should give at least one hour in their daily routine

Introduction:

In modern times, every person's lifestyle and habits are becoming good or bad for physical and mental health. In which Good habits include getting up early, exercising, eating at the right times, being happy and bad habits such as insufficient sleep, bad eating habits, lack of exercise, stress. Stress Increased Obesity Disease which leads to decrease physical fitness.

Going for a walk or jogging is very essential to maintain our physical health it helps us to control our blood pressure, respiratory, weight, Body fat and also increase the immunity against cardiovascular system.

Objectives:

1. To examine the importance of walking for physical and mental health
- 2 To examine the effect on physical ability and causal ability
3. To test the Knowledge of Health education.

Research Method:

For research survey methods were used such as interviews and questionnaires to obtain information. Accordingly to it analysis was done and observational information was presented.

Observation Analysis:

Researchers have done analysis and observation as per the gathered information. For the survey the researcher had choose the Daund town in which he had conversation with total 143 People (Male) and also he observe them on which he has given the following analysis.

Sr. No.	Age Group (Years)	Running (Percentage)	Walking (Percentage)	Total Population
1	45-60	6%	94 %	72
2	35-45	22%	78 %	17
3	26-35	76 %	24 %	12
4	18-26	82 %	12 %	42
Total				143

Following are the observation regarding the people he met in the survey.

1. Every individual can strengthen his muscles power by doing regular exercise.
2. Helps in maintain good mental as well as physical health.
3. Helps to reduced fat and weight.
4. Always fresh mind and full of energy and increases concentration.
5. Helps to Reduces stress and tension and person is always happy.
6. Increases coordination between brain mind and body.
7. Increases metabolic ratio due to which digestion system becomes strong.
8. Improves the body's immune system.
9. Improves stamina and energy resources.
10. Increases in memory due to Increases of neurons in body.
11. Due to exercises body gets tired and people have good sleep which helps to repair body.
12. We can control the cancer gens by doing regular exercises.
13. Improves respiratory system.
14. Exercise flushes out toxins from the body resulting in body cleansing due to which body stays healthy and the person stays energetic.

Conclusion:

1. Regular exercise strengthens muscles power.
2. Regular walking and running gives Good mental and Physical Health.
3. Improves the body's immune system.
4. Decreases problems regarding Sleep.
5. Due to body cleaning person is always energetic.
6. Improves respiratory and digestion system.

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